

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

CO₂ capture integration scenarios and process modelling

ACCSESS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101022487

Coordinated by: SINTEF EnergrAS - www.sintef.no/energy

About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

www.projectaccess.eu

Contact: Kristin.Jordal@sintef.no

Grant Agreement Number:
101022487

Action acronym:
ACCESS

Action full title:
Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable, safe and flexible CCUS

Type of action and topic:
IA
LC-SC3-NZE-5-2020 - Low carbon industrial production using CCUS

Starting date of the action: 2021-05-01
Duration: 48 months

D5.2

CO₂ capture integration scenarios and process modelling

Due delivery date: 2023-04-30
Actual delivery date: 2023-06-28

Organization name of lead participant for this deliverable:
Chalmers tekniska högskola AB

Project co-funded by the European Commission within Horizon2020		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable number:	D5.2
Deliverable title:	CO ₂ capture integration scenarios and process modelling
Work package:	WP 5 CO ₂ capture integration in pulp and paper plants
Lead participant:	CHAL

Author(s)		
Name	Organisation	E-mail
Elin Svensson*	CHAL	elin.svensson@chalmers.se
Simon Harvey	CHAL	simon.harvey@chalmers.se
Henrik Skoglund	CHAL	henrik.skoglund@chalmers.se
Karin Lindgren	SE	karin.lindgren@storaenso.se
Chao Fu	SER	chao.fu@sintef.no
Donghoi Kim	SER	donghoi.kim@sintef.no
Adriana Reyes Lúa	SER	adriana.r.lua@sintef.no
Elettra Vantaggiato	SER	elettra.vantaggiato@sintef.no
Gioia Usai	SPM	gioia.usai@saipem.com

*Lead author

Uploaded and Approval by	Date
Uploaded by lead Beneficiary:	2023/06/12
Approved by WP lead:	2023/06/12
Approved by SP lead (for WP5-8):	2023/06/14
Approved by PMT:	2023/06/28

Keywords
Pulp and paper industry; post-combustion carbon capture; heat integration; lignin extraction

Abstract
<p>This deliverable defines and motivates the CO₂ capture integration scenarios that will be investigated for process integration studies of post combustion capture in pulp and paper mills within work package 5 of the ACCSESS project. The work has focused on Stora Enso's kraft pulp mill located in Skutskär (Sweden) and Stora Enso's recycled paper mill located in Langerbrugge (Belgium). The scenarios include specifications of the flue gases considered for capture for both mills, definitions of the process modelling needed to evaluate the scenarios, as well as descriptions of mill conditions with respect to opportunities for heat integration.</p> <p>The capture process in the capture integration scenarios is assumed to be either a reference amine-based capture process using a blend of 2-amino-2-methyl-propanol (AMP) and Piperazine (PZ) as a solvent or the CO₂ Solutions by Saipem technology. Process models have been developed for both these technologies.</p> <p>The capture integration scenarios for the Langerbrugge mill were defined based on actual, current thermal flows, and heat supply for the capture plant is assumed to be achieved by extracting steam from the existing steam turbine cycles. Assessment of the mill's energy balances indicate that the</p>

total current steam production of the mill (180 MW) should be more than sufficient for covering the heat demand of the mill as well as a new capture plant (approx. 150 MW in total), but would be associated with loss of power generation.

In the scenarios considered for the Skutskär mill, the energy balances were defined assuming optimized heat integration within the mill as well as between the mill and the capture and liquefaction process. The results obtained show that integration of the reference amine-based carbon capture plant strongly affects the energy balances of the mill, leading either to significant losses in power generation or to a significant increase in required utility boiler load. If lignin extraction is assumed to be implemented in the mill, the energy balances become even more constrained when integrating the capture process, since the extraction of lignin reduces the steam production in the recovery boiler. In this scenario, the theoretical energy targets show that additional fuel use in a utility boiler would be required independently of the trade-off between fuel use and power co-generation. This would result in more (biogenic) carbon dioxide being emitted since the emissions from the utility boiler are assumed to not be captured. On the other hand, more biogenic carbon leaves the mill as a valuable by-product, in the form of the extracted lignin.

In the capture scenarios defined to use the CO₂ Solutions by Saipem technology, the heat required for solvent regeneration can be provided by hot water instead of steam. The results from the targeting of excess heat availability in the Skutskär mill indicated that about 30 % of the heat demand can be supplied by excess heat instead of by steam extracted from the mill's steam turbine cycle, assuming that the specific reboiler duty would be similar to that of the reference capture process.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Document Purpose.....	2
1.2 List of Acronyms and abbreviations.....	2
1.3 Relation to other deliverables	2
2 MILL DESCRIPTIONS	3
2.1 Skutskär	3
2.2 Langerbrugge.....	6
3 METHODOLOGY FOR INVESTIGATING HEAT INTEGRATION OPPORTUNITIES	8
3.1 Establishing targets for heat integration of a capture process in the Skutskär mill.....	8
3.2 Identifying heat integration opportunities in the Langerbrugge mill	10
4 PROCESS MODELLING	11
4.1 Capture process with benchmark solvent	11
4.2 CO ₂ Solutions by Saipem	12
4.3 Liquefaction plant.....	14
4.4 Simplified modeling of different process scheme options for CO ₂ capture at the Skutskär mill site	14
5 CAPTURE INTEGRATION SCENARIOS	16
5.1 Capture plant design specifications	17
5.2 Thermal requirements for the capture processes	23
5.3 Definition of heat integration assumptions in the capture integration scenarios	24
6 CONCLUDING SUMMARY	33
7 REFERENCES	35

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies will have an important role in reaching climate targets, by compensating for residual emissions from hard-to-abate sectors and allowing for net negative emissions. Bio-Energy Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) is one of few CDR technologies that can be implemented on a large scale and deliver secure long-term storage of the CO₂ in a relatively cost-efficient way (Fajardy et al., 2021). A major limitation for BECCS, however, is access to a sustainable source of biomass and biogenic carbon to capture. A number of studies have raised concerns that large-scale implementation of purpose-grown biomass for BECCS could have many negative effects including, but not limited to, loss of biodiversity, increased competition for agricultural land, and increased emissions due to land use change (Hanssen et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2016).

Pulp and paper mills have been shown to be promising candidates for BECCS, since they have large existing point sources of biogenic CO₂ emissions, originating from biomass that is used primarily for production of useful materials. Especially in kraft pulp and paper mills, the majority of the emissions result from combustion of black liquor, which is a by-product from the kraft pulping process consisting of a mix of cooking chemicals and organic components from the wood raw material. The processing of the black liquor in the mill's recovery boiler is not only used to supply energy to the process, but also an important part of the regeneration of the chemicals.

Kuparinen et al. (2019) estimated the global technical potential for capture of (mainly biogenic) CO₂ from kraft pulp mills to 135 Mt/a. Recently, Rosa et al. (2021) estimated the technical potential for biogenic CDR from existing point sources in 30 European countries, and found the potential for CDR from pulp and paper plants to be 62 (+/-5) Mt/a.

In WP5 of the ACCESS project, one of the mills selected for the capture integration studies is the Skutskär mill in Sweden. The Skutskär mill is a chemical pulp mill, using the kraft pulping process. Several studies have investigated the integration of post-combustion amine-based carbon capture in the chemical pulping industry. More recent examples include the work by Onarheim et al. (2017a, 2017b) and Nwaoha and Tontiwachwithikul (2019). These studies have investigated heat integration opportunities, effects on mill energy balances, as well as capture and emission avoidance costs for different capture configurations applied to different flue gas sources in the mills. Although there is commonly excess heat available from the pulping processes, opportunities to recover this to drive the capture processes are typically limited due to the high temperatures required for solvent regeneration in an amine-based capture process. This makes it interesting to study the integration potential for emerging capture technologies that may allow the heat requirement to be covered by heat supplied at lower temperatures. One such technology is the CO₂ Solutions technology from Saipem, which is considered in some of the capture integration scenarios defined in this deliverable.

With increasing demands for renewable carbon resources from other sectors, the pulp and paper industry is under pressure to strive towards better utilization of the biomass resource, and to have a larger share of the biomass feedstock converted into valuable products. This can be enabled by integration of new technologies and processes for extraction and valorization of side streams from the pulp by-products. In particular, there are opportunities for extracting renewable and value-added chemicals from the kraft black liquor (Akbari et al., 2018; Pola et al., 2022). One such possibility is the extraction of lignin (Hubbe et al., 2019), which can be further processed into biochemicals, biomaterials or biofuels (Téguia et al., 2017). When investigating a potential future integration of carbon capture in a pulp or paper mill, it is thus also necessary to consider the

expected strategic development in the mill and investigate how new process concepts may affect the potential for carbon capture and the site-wide energy balances. This deliverable defines capture integration scenarios which include the potential implementation of lignin extraction as one such future strategic development in a chemical pulp mill.

Although the largest potential for biogenic carbon capture in pulp and paper industry is from chemical (kraft) mills, there are opportunities for carbon capture also in other types of mills. While the majority of kraft mills in EU are located in Sweden and Finland, with long distances to potential geological storage sites for the captured CO₂, other types of mills might be better located relative to the development of transport and storage infrastructure. The second mill selected for capture integration studies in WP5 of the ACCSESS project is the Langerbrugge mill in Belgium, which is a recycled paper mill. Recycled paper mills are very common in many countries within the EU, which makes a study on this type of mill very relevant for further work on potential deployment of BECCS in the European pulp and paper industry. Studies on carbon capture in recycled paper mills are very difficult to find in previously published literature.

1.1 Document Purpose

This report defines and motivates the CO₂ capture integration scenarios that will be investigated for process integration studies of post combustion capture in pulp and paper mills within Work Package 5 (WP5) of the ACCSESS project. The scenarios include specifications of the flue gases considered for capture, definitions of the process modelling needed to evaluate the scenarios, as well as descriptions of mill conditions with respect to opportunities for heat integration.

1.2 List of Acronyms and abbreviations

AMP	2-Amino-2-Methyl-Propanol
BECCS	Bio-Energy Carbon Capture and Storage
BFB	Bubbling Fluidized Bed
CA	Carbonic Anhydrase
CFB	Circulating Fluidized Bed
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
DH	District Heating
DCC	Direct Contact Cooler
DIP	De-Inking Plant
GCC	Grand Composite Curve
LULUCF	Land-Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry
MEA	MonoEthanolAmine
OVHD	OVerHeaD
PfR	Paper for Recycling
PZ	PiperaZine
RDF	Refuse Derived Fuel

1.3 Relation to other deliverables

The capture integration scenarios defined in this deliverable will be evaluated and compared with regards to techno-economic performance in further work in WP5, and results will be presented in deliverable D5.3. Subsequently, the techno-economic assessment of different capture integration scenarios for pulp and paper mills will serve as input for evaluation the potential for carbon dioxide removal in European industry (in D5.4) and, together with results from other work packages, provide input to D10.6 on prospective CCUS chains in Europe for different sectors.

2 MILL DESCRIPTIONS

Two distinctly different mills were selected for the capture integration studies in WP5: A mill producing market pulp from virgin feedstock using a chemical pulping process, and a mill producing paper from recycled feedstock.

The Skutskär mill is a kraft pulp mill (a chemical pulp mill). Kraft pulp (and paper) mills have been shown to be promising candidates for capture of biogenic CO₂, since they have large existing point sources of biogenic emissions as a result of combustion of by-products from the processing of the pulp wood feedstock. Since the biogenic emissions of kraft pulp and paper mills are closely associated with the processing of biomass into useful materials, the implementation of kraft mill-based BECCS value chains faces less risk of criticism compared to implementation of large-scale deployment of new BECCS installations, which risk leading to competition with land use for food production, adverse effects on biodiversity or Land-Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) emissions. Furthermore, in modern kraft pulp mills (without integrated paper production) the steam generated from combustion of bio-based by-products is typically more than sufficient to cover the heat and electricity demand for the whole mill, which enables these mills to be net exporters of electricity, biomass fuel and/or heat. This excess of energy makes CO₂ capture especially promising in (non-integrated) kraft pulp mills, since (at least parts of) the energy demand for capture potentially could be covered without additional energy supply. This is not the case for integrated pulp and paper mills where the pulp production process is followed by paper or board production, which is associated with additional steam and electricity requirements. Consequently, integrated mills have a less favorable energy balance, and they are typically net importers electricity and sometimes also of fuel. The Skutskär mill is located on the east coast of Sweden, with good access to a port for transport of captured CO₂, but with a long distance to the closest storage sites currently being developed.

The Langerbrugge mill is a recycled newsprint and magazine paper mill in northwest Belgium, a promising location with respect to potential access to transport of CO₂. The mill has two power plants, which provide process steam to the mill and district heating to nearby industrial plants, as well as a substantial share of the electric power needed in the mill. The power boilers use a wide range of fuels including imported waste wood and RDF (Refuse Derived Fuel), sewage sludge, bio-sludge and sludge from the De-Inking Plant (DIP). Previously, the power plants ran predominantly on biomass fuels. However, since 2021, the mill is no longer eligible for subsidies for green (bio-based) electricity generation. Due to this, and the limited availability of biomass fuels, the mill has increased the share of low-cost waste fuels, mainly Refuse Derived Fuels (RDF), but also waste wood. RDF is a fuel produced from, e.g., municipal solid waste, which is treated to be more effectively used as a fuel. The availability is significant in the region, and the economic benefit is high thanks to the reception fee paid to the incineration plant for all types of waste fuels. However, due to the fossil content of RDF (mainly from plastics), the share of fossil fuels and CO₂ emissions from the mill has increased. This makes it interesting to consider CCS at the mill, as a means to compensate for the fossil emissions by negative emissions from Bio-CCS.

2.1 Skutskär

The Stora Enso Skutskär mill (see Figure 2.1) is a kraft pulp mill producing about 0.5 million tonnes of pulp per year from birch and conifer feedstock. The mill is a stand-alone market pulp mill, which means it does not have integrated paper production.

Figure 2.1: The Skutskär pulp mill in Sweden

A simplified flow chart of the kraft pulp process is shown in Figure 2.2. In the cooking plant, lignin is dissolved and separated from cellulose fibers using white liquor, which is a water-based solution with sodium hydroxide and sodium sulfide. The separated cellulose fibers are further processed into the finished pulp product, while the liquor with the dissolved lignin and the spent cooking chemicals, now called black liquor, is processed in the recovery cycle to regenerate the cooking chemicals and recover the energy content of the organic components (mainly lignin and hemicelluloses) of the liquor.

Figure 2.2: Simplified process flow chart of the kraft pulp process

For efficient combustion of the black liquor, the water content must be reduced significantly. This is done in the evaporation section where the dry solids content is increased from about 20 % to 70-72 %. The evaporation section consists of a series of integrated evaporator effects where the first one uses low pressure steam as heat source, and the following effects use vapor from the previous effect to drive the evaporation.

The concentrated black liquor from the evaporation section is sprayed into the recovery boilers, where the organic components are combusted and some of the chemical reactions necessary to recover the cooking chemicals take place. The combustion generates large amounts of biogenic carbon dioxide in the flue gas. However, some of the carbon that enters with the black liquor is also converted to carbonates, which leave the recovery boiler together with the other inorganic chemicals as a smelt, which is dissolved in water to form so-called green liquor.

In the causticization section, green liquor is mixed with burnt lime (calcium oxide) to form white liquor. This is achieved in a series of reactions, where the burnt lime first reacts with the water of the green liquor, forming calcium hydroxide (slaked lime), which in turn reacts with the sodium carbonate of the green liquor to form sodium hydroxide and calcium carbonate. The calcium carbonate is separated from the liquor and sent to the lime kiln to be regenerated into burnt lime, and the liquor is now regenerated into white liquor, that can be reused in the cooking. The regeneration of burnt lime from calcium carbonate in the lime kilns requires energy at high temperatures. At the studied mill, this energy is supplied using tall oil pitch as fuel. Tall oil pitch is a biofuel, which is a residue from the processing of crude tall oil into tall oil. When the calcium carbonate is oxidized to calcium oxide, carbon dioxide is formed, which will exit the lime kiln with the flue gas. Through the series of reactions explained above, this carbon *originates* from the organic components in the black liquor and is thus considered to be biogenic carbon dioxide. Since the lime kiln flue gas contains carbon dioxide both from the oxidization of the lime and from the combustion of (bio-)fuel, the carbon dioxide concentration of the flue gas is usually high.

Pulp mills are energy-intensive industrial plants with large amounts of heat and electricity being consumed. However, like most modern energy-efficient market kraft pulp mills, the Skutskär mill is essentially self-sufficient in heat supply from internally generated fuel by-products. In fact, the mill currently operates completely free from fossil fuels. Most of the steam demand (including steam for turbines, which cover a large share of the mill's electric power demand) is covered by steam generated through black liquor combustion in the mill's recovery boilers. To a smaller extent, the mill's steam demand is currently also supplemented by combustion of bark and other internally generated wood fuels in the power boiler.

The steam generated in the boilers is fed to a high-pressure steam header. This steam is expanded through a back-pressure, extraction steam turbine, or, if necessary, through direct expansion valves to medium-pressure and low-pressure steam headers. Pressure and temperature specifications for the steam headers are presented in Table 2.1. In the mill, medium-pressure and low-pressure steam is used in various parts of the process, mainly to supply heat through heat exchangers, but also by mixing the steam with process streams directly.

Table 2.1. Steam header properties for the steam utility system.

Steam utility headers	Pressure [bar(g)]	Temperature [°C]
High-pressure steam	56	440
Medium-pressure steam	11	190
Low-pressure steam	3	145

Process cooling in the mill is achieved via the secondary heat recovery system. Process streams are cooled with water, which is heated to warm or hot water temperatures and sent to the water tanks of the secondary heating system. The water is then used for heating and as process or cleaning water in various parts of the mill. Additional cooling at the mill is done using cooling towers to cool dirty water before wastewater treatment.

The sources of CO₂ emissions in the mill are the flue gases from the two recovery boilers, lime kilns and the power boiler. While the recovery boilers and lime kilns are operated based on demand for recovering chemicals from the black liquor, the power boiler is operated to balance total steam production with the process steam demands. Consequently, the load of the power boiler varies quite significantly, and will also differ between the integration scenarios.

2.2 Langerbrugge

Langerbrugge mill in northwest Belgium (see Figure 2.3) is a recycled newsprint and magazine paper mill. The mill has two paper machines and an annual capacity to produce 540 000 t/a of paper from about 650 000 t/a of sorted paper for recycling (PfR).

Figure 2.3: The Langerbrugge paper mill in Belgium

Figure 2.4 shows an overview of the production processes and the power plants at the Langerbrugge mill.

Figure 2.4: Overview of the processes at the recycle paper production mill in Langerbrugge

The sorted paper is first sent to the de-inking plants (DIPs). The first stage here is the pulping stage where the paper is chopped to smaller pieces, and water and chemicals are added. The resulting slurry is screened to remove unwanted components as rejects. Finally, in the main de-inking stage, printing ink and sticky components (e.g., from glue, other adhesives or plastics) are removed using a flotation process. This part of the process must be operated at low temperatures around 50 °C. The ink ends up in a sludge (DIP sludge), which is sent to the power plants for incineration. The deinked pulp is sent to the paper making process.

The paper machines require a high-temperature heat supply in the form of 2.2 bar(g) steam. Two combined heat and power (CHP) plants provide all the process steam required at the mill and more than 70 % of the electric needed. In one of the power plants, steam is produced at 80 bar and then expanded to the 2.2. bar steam pressure level in a back-pressure turbine. In the other power plant steam is produced at 60 bar and 2.2 bar process stream is extracted from a condensing turbine. Since 2016, the mill also delivers high-temperature (> 120 °C) district heating to Volvo Cars, located on the other side of the canal in Ghent.

3 METHODOLOGY FOR INVESTIGATING HEAT INTEGRATION OPPORTUNITIES

Due to differences in overall energy balances and complexity of the thermal energy systems of the two mills, different methodologies were chosen for investigating the potential for heat integration between the mills and the capture and liquefaction plants.

3.1 Establishing targets for heat integration of a capture process in the Skutskär mill

To investigate how the integration of carbon capture would affect the heat balances and power co-generation potential at the Skutskär mill, an approach based on Pinch Analysis (see e.g. Klemeš, 2023) was used. More specifically, pinch-based tools were applied to establish targets for heat recovery through optimized heat cascades as well as corresponding minimum utility requirements for different mill configurations. Next, the theoretical targets for minimum hot and cold utility, as well as targets for minimum fuel use and maximized co-generation were compared between the different mill configurations. The approach closely follows the method proposed by Svensson et al. (2019) for estimation of excess heat and co-generation targets.

One of the strengths of applying an energy targeting approach is that the graphical representation of the optimized heat cascade, i.e. the GCC, can be conveniently used for visualizing the potential for heat integration between a process (e.g., the mill) and its utility system or another process (e.g., a capture process). This also avoids the need to collect information regarding existing process heat recovery solutions in the mill, as well as the need to know how the heat recovery system for the new processes will be designed. However, it should be noted that the GCC represents a process with maximum internal heat recovery and does not consider any constraints of the process layout and design besides the minimum temperature difference for heat exchange. Such ideal heat integration is unlikely to occur in an actual process plant, and especially not in an existing plant that has been revamped regularly over a long period of time. On the other hand, the assumption of ideal heat recovery allows for a consistent and fair comparison between different configurations, avoiding the risk of comparing one optimized configuration with a non-optimized one. Furthermore, the heat integrated process may be a better representation of a future scenario in which further steps have been taken to improve heat recovery in the mill.

The optimal heat cascades are established by solving a linear programming problem to identify the theoretical minimum hot and cold utility demands for each investigated mill configuration, assuming a minimum temperature difference for heat exchange of 10 K. The process streams representing the heat sources and sinks of the mill form the so-called background process. In this context, high temperature heat from combustion of black liquor in the recovery boiler is also considered to be a process-inherent heat source (i.e., the steam from the recovery boiler is not seen as utility steam), since the processing of black liquor in the recovery boiler is a necessary step in the recovery of chemicals. The process streams related to the carbon capture and liquefaction process form the foreground process. With the linear programming model, the potential matching of the heat cascades for the foreground and background processes can be evaluated numerically to provide an indication of how well the carbon capture plant can be heat integrated with the mill. The GCCs representing the respective heat cascades can also be plotted in the same figure in order to visualize the potential integration between the two processes (see e.g. Kemp and Shiun Lim, 2020, where this is referred to as splitting the GCC). An example of such split GCC analysis for the mill and the capture process is shown in Figure 5.6 in Section 5.3.1.

Next, it is estimated how the integration of the carbon capture and liquefaction process would affect the potential for steam turbine power generation in the mill. This analysis is also performed using the energy targeting approach based on optimized heat cascades. To find the potential for power co-generation, the process heat cascade is consequently optimized again, now assuming ideally integrated steam turbine cycles. In order to apply the linear programming model, a simplified steam cycle is assumed with turbine extractions limited to the existing steam levels of the mill, and an assumed value for the isentropic efficiency of the turbine. Consequently, for each capture integration scenario, the energy targeting problem is solved as a linear programming problem, where the heat cascades of the processes and the steam cycle are optimized to minimize primary hot utility (i.e., fuel use) and maximize power generation. The trade-off between the objectives was handled by weighting them into one single objective function. Two different weightings were considered. As a first case, hot utility (fuel use) was given a sufficiently high weight to ensure that the objective of minimized fuel use is always prioritized over maximized power generation. With this weighting, power generation would only be achieved if there is sufficient heat from the recovery boiler to generate all steam necessary for process heating as well as steam for turbine operation. As a second case, the weighting for (back-pressure) power generation is set high enough to prioritize maximized power generation in back-pressure steam turbines over minimized fuel use. With this weighting, additional fuel use may be needed. The energy targeting computations are performed using the in-house Matlab-based tool Mat4PI (Morandin, 2017).

The integration with the steam turbine cycle can also be visualized using split GCCs, as shown in Figure 3.1 (see also Harvey et al., 2023 for further information about energy targeting for integration of steam turbine CHP). In this case, the stream data for the integrated carbon capture and pulping process (reference capture integration scenario for the Skutskär mill) was used to construct the GCC for the background process, while the steam turbine cycle was represented as the foreground GCC.

Figure 3.1. Illustration of the integration between the processes and the steam turbine cycle, represented as split GCCs. The background process GCC represents ideal heat integration between heat sources and sinks in the Skutskär mill equipped with the reference amine-based capture process, and includes unavoidable high-temperature heat from the recovery boiler.

3.2 Identifying heat integration opportunities in the Langerbrugge mill

The production process in the Langerbrugge mill is significantly less complex than the kraft pulping process used in the Skutskär mill, and leaves very limited opportunities for improved heat recovery. Therefore, the Langerbrugge scenarios are defined with current thermal flows instead of thermal energy targets.

Furthermore, one of the reasons for applying an energy targeting approach for the Skutskär mill is that this enables a consistent and fair comparison between the reference capture integration scenario, and a scenario which includes an assumed strategic development in the mill, for which a complete and final design is not available. However, for the Langerbrugge mill, no such scenarios were defined which include comparable strategic mill development.

Consequently, any heat integration between the mill and the capture plant at the Langerbrugge site is assumed to be achieved primarily via the steam utility system.

4 PROCESS MODELLING

Process models were established for both a reference amine-based capture technology and the CO₂ Solutions by Saipem technology. In particular, the models include operating characteristics (solvent regeneration heat requirement and temperature level as well as other solvent specific data of relevance) of the capture process for both the Reference solvent and the CO₂ Solutions by Saipem solvent. In Task 5.3, these models will be used to simulate the capture scenarios as defined in this report, in order to estimate equipment costs and capital costs for the capture and liquefaction plants.

In addition, a tool developed for simplified modelling and comparison of structurally different process scheme options for capture of CO₂ from several emission sources on the same site was used. This modelling tool, which is introduced in Section 4.4, was used for a preliminary screening of the best capture plant configuration for the Skutskär mill site.

4.1 Capture process with benchmark solvent

The reference CO₂ capture process in this project is a post combustion amine absorption process, since this is one of the most mature options for carbon capture from flue gases, which is also well-suited for retrofit of existing industrial plants, such as pulp and paper mills. The reference capture process was assumed to use the AMP (2-amino-2-methyl-propanol) -PZ (piperazine) solvent that has been suggested as the new benchmark solvent for post-combustion carbon capture (Feron et al., 2020).

A simplified flowsheet of the CO₂ capture process using AMP-PZ solvent is shown in Figure 4.1. It is assumed that a common absorber is used to treat the mixed flue gases from all considered stacks. The CO₂-rich flue gas feed is cooled to around 40°C before being sent to an absorber for CO₂ absorption. A water wash section is placed at the top of the absorber to recover solvents from the CO₂-lean flue gases. The rich solvent is extracted from the absorber bottom and sent to the stripper for regeneration. The CO₂ captured is extracted from the stripper top and sent to the subsequent conditioning unit. The solvent is thereafter regenerated i.e., lean solvent is extracted from the stripper bottom and sent back to the absorber for reuse. A lean-rich heat exchanger is used for heat recovery from the lean solvent.

Figure 4.1: Flowsheet of the reference amine-based carbon capture process. Adapted from Voldsund et al. (2019).

The CO₂ capture process was simulated using rate-based models in Aspen Plus V10. The eNRTL property method was used. The reactions involved, the equilibrium and kinetics parameters and interaction parameters were taken from Aspen Plus default library models for AMP and PZ solvents and literature (Li et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2017). The process was simulated with flue gas data representing normal mill operation as specified in Sections 5.1.1 and 5.1.3.

The carbon capture process requires both heating and cooling in different parts of the process. These thermal energy requirements were established with the developed model and used as input for the heat integration study for the scenarios in which the reference solvent is considered (see Section 5.2.1).

The CO₂ leaving the stripper was further assumed to be conditioned in a liquefaction plant to the conditions required for ship transport, before being stored in a buffer storage, see Section 4.3.

4.2 CO₂ Solutions by Saipem

The CO₂ Solutions technology is a post-combustion CO₂ capture technology based on flue gas washing using a water-based solution containing potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃) and an enzyme. The enzyme, a protein that acts as a biocatalyst, is a proprietary strain of Carbonic Anhydrase (CA) enhanced for application for CO₂ capture through an exclusive directed evolution process. The CA enzyme accelerates the conversion of CO₂ into bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) as the CO₂ enters the solvent solution, as well as the reverse reaction (bicarbonate to CO₂) when the CO₂ is released during solvent regeneration.

Figure 4.2 shows a simplified process flow diagram of the carbon capture technology. The incoming flue gas is routed to the suction of the flue gas blower, dedicated to overcoming the gas flow path pressure drop and ensuring the correct pressure value at the absorber inlet. If necessary, the flue gas is cooled down in the flue gas cooler and, thereafter, the flue gas is sent to the quench column, which provides direct contact gas cooling and particulate cleaning in a single step. The quench column top gas is routed to the absorber bottom where the cooled and cleaned gas is contacted counter-currently with the lean solvent (i.e., a water-based solution containing potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃) and the proprietary enzyme), which is fed to the top of the absorber column. The rich solvent, containing the captured CO₂ in the form of potassium bicarbonate (KHCO₃), flows down to the absorption column bottom, while the treated gas flows upwards to the column top and is released to the atmosphere.

The rich solvent stream from the bottom of the absorber is pumped by the rich solvent pump, through the lean/rich heat exchanger, to the top of the stripping column. In the stripping column, CO₂ is stripped from the rich solvent by decreasing the pressure and increasing the temperature. The rich solvent is fed to the top of the column and flows downward in the structured packing, in counter-current flow against the vapour stream rising from the solvent reboiler. The lean solvent pump sends the lean solvent from the stripper bottom to the lean/rich heat exchanger where it is cooled down by heat exchange with the rich solvent leaving the absorber bottom. The lean solvent is further cooled by cooling water in the lean solvent cooler and then fed to the top of the absorber.

The CO₂-rich stream from the top of the stripping column is routed to the overhead (OVHD) condensate separator via the OVHD condenser, where the condensed water is separated. The CO₂-rich gas from the top of the OVHD condensate separator is then sent to the compressor. The compressor maintains the vacuum inside the stripping column at the appropriate level and provides the CO₂ boosting pressure up to 1 bar(g).

Figure 4.2: Simplified process flow diagram for the CO2 Solutions technology.

The carbon capture process was modelled using rate-based models in Protreac 6.6 (Optimized Gas Treating Inc., 2021). The enzyme library property package was used. This model will be used in subsequent project tasks to simulate the process for the capture integration scenarios defined to use the CO₂ Solutions technology, using flue gas specifications as specified in Sections 5.1.1 and 5.1.3.

4.3 Liquefaction plant

In the liquefaction plant, the captured CO₂ is conditioned for ship transport. A simplified flowsheet of the liquefaction plant is shown in Figure 4.3. In the liquefaction process, the CO₂ rich stream from the capture process is first compressed in a multi-stage compressor train with intercoolers and liquefied using an ammonia refrigeration cycle. In the compression train, condensed water is removed from the feed gas through phase separators. Deep water removal is achieved with a dehydration unit. Other impurities, mainly O₂, are removed as a purge gas after the liquefaction, resulting in a minor loss of the CO₂. The process also includes a recirculation of flash gas that is generated during a throttling step for further purification of the liquefied CO₂. The liquefied CO₂ has a pressure of 16 bar(a), a temperature of -26 °C, and is purified to fulfil the Northern Lights specifications (Equinor, 2019). The modeling of the liquefaction plant is described in detail in Deng et al (2019).

The liquefaction process has thermal energy requirements (cooling duties), which are represented in the model. Simulations of the liquefaction plant will be used to establish these cooling duties as input for the heat integration analysis for the different capture integration scenarios.

Figure 4.3: Simplified flowsheet of the liquefaction process. Adapted from Deng et al (2019).

4.4 Simplified modeling of different process scheme options for CO₂ capture at the Skutskär mill site

The presence of multiple CO₂ sources in a single industrial site provides different process scheme options for the CO₂ capture. For example, it is possible to mix two or more flue gas streams. In addition, the mixing can be implemented in different points of the process, such as upstream of the absorption column, or downstream, as shown in Figure 4.4. The choice of capture process configuration has an impact on the equipment sizes and the total costs of the plant. It will also be affected by the layout of the existing site (i.e., available space and distances between flue gas sources and potential areas for the new plants) and the economy of scale. For this reason, different scheme options for the Skutskär mill were analyzed through a simplified modelling study.

Figure 4.4: Examples of CO₂ capture configuration schemes for industrial sites with multiple emission sources. The placement of absorber (blue box) and regeneration and compression (green box) sections indicates whether these sections are placed closer to the flue gas point source or to the point where CO₂ leaves the site (CO₂ to fence). The arrows thus indicate where the longest ducting or piping is required, with the width of the arrow illustrating the successively smaller volume flows to be transported along the capture and compression chain.

Simulation results were obtained using the iCCS tool developed by SINTEF Energy Research (Anantharaman et al., 2013; Biermann et al., 2022; Jakobsen et al., 2014; Roussanaly et al., 2014, 2013; Roussanaly and Anantharaman, 2017). The tool assumes the use of monoethanolamine (MEA) as solvent and integrates some first principle models (e.g., for pressure drops) and simplified models (e.g., regression models) describing the individual steps in the CO₂ capture process (i.e., direct contact cooler (DCC), absorber, desorber, and conditioning for transport/storage), along with ducting and utilities. Using the flue gas data, all the relevant physical data (i.e., pressure drops, intermediate and final compositions and temperatures, and equipment sizes) are calculated and used to perform techno-economic analyses. The best option in terms of estimated costs and equipment sizes can then be selected.

5 CAPTURE INTEGRATION SCENARIOS

In this section, different scenarios for integrating a capture process in the selected mills are defined. An overview of the capture integration scenarios is given in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Overview of capture integration scenarios.

The scenarios consider internal heat recovery when relevant. Different product mixes for a multi-product biorefinery mill were considered by including a scenario for the Skutskär mill in which lignin is extracted as a novel product (see Section 5.1.2). The design specifications for the capture plant in the different scenarios are further defined in Section 5.1. One reference scenario, assuming integration of the reference amine-based capture technology (with the AMP/PZ solvent), was defined for each mill and used for benchmarking against the corresponding scenario with integration of the CO₂ Solutions technology from Saipem. Heat pumping opportunities are discussed as part of the reference scenario for the Skutskär mill (see Section 5.3.1.4).

In the Skutskär mill, the reference scenario is defined by capture from the mixed flue gases of the two recovery boilers and the lime kilns using the reference capture technology. The choice of considering that all flue gases are mixed and sent to a common absorber was supported by preliminary screening of different process scheme options, as described in Section 4.4. All scenarios considered for the Skutskär mill are defined assuming optimized heat integration within the mill as well as between the mill and the capture and liquefaction process. The resulting energy targets are established using the methodology described in Section 3.1, and examples of results are presented in Section 5.3.1.

Previous studies on carbon capture in pulp and paper mills typically assume that mills implementing carbon capture will maintain the current configuration and operation. However, new biomass conversion processes are increasingly being deployed in pulp and paper mills to improve resource efficiency and extract more valuable bio-based products from the wood. Such strategic mill development will effectively convert the pulp mills to multi-product biorefineries, and lead to more of the biogenic carbon ending up in products. Consequently, less carbon would be available for capture in flue gases of, e.g., the recovery boiler. One of the more mature large-scale

opportunities for increased biomass valorization in kraft pulp mills is lignin extraction. In our analysis of carbon capture in the Skutskär mill, two different scenarios are defined for the mill processes, where the first corresponds to the current mill configuration and normal operation (reference scenario), and the second assumes that lignin extraction has been implemented in the mill. For the scenario with lignin extraction, the capture and liquefaction process will not be modelled explicitly, but results estimated based on simulations performed for the reference scenario will be used (see Section 5.1.2 and 5.3.1.1).

To consider different possibilities to manage the effect of carbon capture integration on the steam balances of the Skutskär mill, scenarios were also defined representing different trade-offs between fuel use and co-generation of power. These are described in Table 5.1 together with brief descriptions of the two different mill configurations with integrated carbon capture, which were investigated for the Skutskär mill.

Table 5.1: Overview of investigated mill configurations and optimization trade-offs for the Skutskär mill. In the heat integration analysis, all mill configurations are represented by their optimized heat cascades for a given minimum temperature difference for heat exchange.

Mill configuration	Description
Carbon capture only (Reference capture integration scenario)	Existing mill (assuming annual average heat flows and temperature data) with a heat integrated carbon capture and liquefaction process
Lignin extraction and carbon capture	Mill with lignin extraction plant and with a heat integrated carbon capture and liquefaction process
Optimization trade-offs	Description
Minimized fuel use	The use of additional (biomass) fuel in utility boilers is minimized. Co-generation of electricity is considered only if enough heat is generated in the recovery boiler to allow for combined heat and power production
Maximized power generation	Power generation in back-pressure steam turbines is maximized up to the point where back-pressure steam from the turbine matches the minimum process net heating demand. Condensing turbine operation is not considered.

For the Langerbrugge mill, the reference scenario is defined by capture from the mixed flue gases of the two boilers. The production process in the Langerbrugge mill is significantly less complex than the one in the Skutskär mill, with very limited opportunities for improved heat recovery. Consequently, the two scenarios defined for the Langerbrugge mill assume heat integration between the capture process and the mill based on actual, current thermal flows (rather than energy targets as for the Skutskär mill scenarios). Heat supply for the capture plant is assumed to be achieved by extracting steam from the existing steam turbine cycles.

5.1 Capture plant design specifications

For all capture integration scenarios, the capture rate is assumed to be 90 %, and the captured CO₂ at the stripper outlet is assumed to have a CO₂ content of at least 98 vol%, a minimum pressure of 1.9 bar (a) and a temperature of 28 °C (see also Section 4.3).

It is further assumed that utilities needed for the capture plant can be provided from the host site based on demand.

5.1.1 Flue gases considered for carbon capture in the Skutskär mill

The CO₂ from the power boiler is not considered for capture, partly because the power boiler can have large operational variations, and partly because the load of the power boiler, and consequently its CO₂ emissions, is highly dependent on the energy balances of the integrated processes at the mill site, and would therefore differ considerably between the different integration scenarios.

Table 5.2 reports flue gas data for the CO₂ emission sources in the mill that are considered for capture in the Skutskär capture integration scenarios. Based on the results from a preliminary screening of different capture configuration options (see Section 5.1.4), it is assumed that the flue gases will be mixed before being sent to a common absorber. All flue gases are assumed to be sent to the capture plant with a pressure of 1 bar (a). In total, the recovery boilers and lime kilns emit approximately 1.1 million tonnes of CO₂ per year.

Table 5.2: Flue gas flows and temperatures according to the design specifications for the capture process in the Skutskär mill. The flue gases are assumed to be mixed before being sent to the capture plant.

Emission source	Flue gas flow [m ³ /h dry]	Temperature [°C]	Operation [h/year]
Lime kilns (LK)	45 000	125*	8 400
Small recovery boiler (SP6)	100 000	54	8 400
Large recovery boiler (SP7)	300 000	125*	8 400

* Current flue gas temperatures are 170 °C (SP7) and 300 °C (LK), but flue gas coolers are assumed to be implemented before the flue gases are sent to the capture plant

The two recovery boilers have separate stacks, and different flue gas treatments installed. Flue gases from the larger recovery boiler pass through a convective section with a superheater and economizer before being passed through an electrostatic filter and then sent to the stack. In the smaller recovery boiler, the flue gases also go through a superheater first, but then pass through an electrostatic filter before going to the economizer. These flue gases also pass through a scrubber, where they are further cleaned and cooled before being sent to the stack. Table 5.3 shows the composition of the flue gases sent to the capture plant.

Table 5.3: Flue gas composition for the individual flue gas sources in the Skutskär mill, which will be mixed before being sent to the capture plant.

Component	Large recovery boiler (SP7)	Small recovery boiler (SP6)	Lime kilns (LK)	Unit of measure
H ₂ O	20.0	13	28	mol%
CO ₂	12.0	10.4	15.8	mol% wet
N ₂	64.8	70.6	52.7	mol% wet
O ₂	3.2	6.1	3.5	mol% wet
H ₂ S	0.8	0.9	0.4	ppmv wet
SO ₂	4.0	10	19	ppmv wet
NO _x	80.0	75	145	ppmv wet
CO	4.0	17	20	ppmv wet

5.1.2 Effect of lignin extraction on the capture integration potential in the Skutskär mill

The predominant way of extracting lignin from black liquor is by precipitation (Pola et al., 2022). The lignin is extracted by removing a part of the black liquor flow from the evaporation plant and acidifying it with CO₂ to lower the solubility of lignin in the liquor. The precipitated lignin is then separated from the remaining liquor through press filters. The crude lignin from the first press filters is then further purified by further lowering the pH value, washing and dewatering it in a second press filter. A big advantage for lignin extraction of having a CO₂ capture unit in the mill is that the need for CO₂ for the lignin precipitation can be fulfilled by captured CO₂, thereby avoiding the need to purchase CO₂.

In this study, it was assumed that 6.94 t/h of lignin is extracted from the black liquor. This corresponds to 0.12 tonnes of lignin per air-dried tonne of pulp, which is well within the range of feasible extraction rates reported in literature (Välimäki et al., 2010), and similar to plants in commercial operation (Haaker, 2015).

The major effect of lignin extraction in the mill is connected to the operation of the recovery boilers. When lignin is extracted from the black liquor, it will no longer be combusted in the recovery boiler, thereby reducing the amount of CO₂ (available for capture) in the flue gases. The reduction is estimated to 2.26 tonnes of CO₂ per tonne of lignin, based on a carbon content of lignin of 65.1 wt% (Tomani, 2010). This leads to a reduction in total amount of CO₂ captured from 132 t/h to 120 t/h.

The CO₂ that is added to the precipitation vessel (estimated to 0.28 tonnes of CO₂ per tonne of lignin) is assumed to react with the cooking chemicals of the liquor and form carbonates. The carbonates will remain with the liquor until the causticization unit, and the carbon finally is released as CO₂ with the flue gas of the lime kiln. Since the CO₂ in the lime kiln is assumed to be captured, this will result in a small recirculation of CO₂.

Overall, since the flue gases are assumed to be mixed before being sent to the capture plant, the increased release of CO₂ from the lime kilns and the changed reaction conditions in the recovery boiler are assumed to have only a minor effect on the concentration of CO₂ in the mixed flue gases. In this work, it is assumed that this effect is small enough to not affect the heating and cooling requirements of the carbon capture and liquefaction process per tonne of captured CO₂.

Due to the reduced load on the recovery boiler, the overall steam balances of the mill will also be affected by the lignin extraction (see Section 5.3.1.1). One way to cover the lost steam production is to increase the load on the (existing or a new) power boiler. This will however imply that new (biogenic) emissions appear in the mill. In order to estimate these emissions, which are not considered for capture, the CO₂ emission factor of the solid wood fuel used in the power boiler was assumed to be 96 g/MJ and the fuel to heat efficiency of the boiler was assumed to be 85 % independently of load.

5.1.3 Flue gases considered for carbon capture in the Langerbrugge mill

Table 5.4 reports flue gas data for the CO₂ emission sources in the mill that are considered for capture in the Langerbrugge capture integration scenarios. It is assumed that the flue gases are mixed before being sent to a common absorber. All flue gases are assumed to be sent to the capture plant at a pressure of 1 bar(a). In total, the two boilers emit approximately 0.6 million tonnes of CO₂ per year. Table 5.5 shows the composition of the flue gases sent to the capture plant.

Table 5.4: Flue gas flows and temperatures according to the design specifications for the capture process in the Langerbrugge mill. The flue gases are assumed to be mixed before being sent to the capture plant.

Emission source	Flue gas flow [Nm ³ /h dry]	Temperature [°C]	Operation [h/year]
Steam boiler, EC1	100 000	65	8 000
Steam boiler, EC2	200 000	60	8 000

Table 5.5: Flue gas composition for the individual flue gas sources in the Langerbrugge mill, which will be mixed before being sent to the capture plant.

Component	Steam boiler (EC1)	Steam boiler (EC2)	Unit of measure
H ₂ O	20	15	vol%
CO ₂	15	12	vol% dry
O ₂	4	6.4	vol% dry
Dust	0.5	0.3	mg/Nm ³ dry
NO ₂	107	100	mg/Nm ³ dry
CO	7.5	2.9	mg/Nm ³ dry
SO ₂	0	0.7	mg/Nm ³ dry
HCl	0.05	0.1	mg/Nm ³ dry
C _x H _y	N/A	1.4	mg/Nm ³ dry

5.1.4 Screening of different capture configuration options for the Skutskär mill site

As introduced in Section 4.4, a simplified modeling study was performed to evaluate the best process scheme option to implement CO₂ capture for the multiple CO₂ sources present at the Skutskär mill site. The study was performed using the flue gas data presented in Section 5.1.1. The plant layout was considered through openly available satellite images (Figure 5.2) to determine the location of the CO₂ sources, evaluate the required ducting lengths and the location of possible areas for the direct contact cooling (DCC), absorption, desorption and conditioning units (Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.2: Satellite view of the Skutskär mill. Satellite image from Hitta.se (2023).

Figure 5.3: Layout analysis and CO₂ source locations for the Skutskär mill. Satellite image from Google Maps (2023).

When the cooling and the absorption is performed for a single source, it was assumed that the equipment will be in the vicinity of each source. When the flue gas streams are mixed, it was assumed that the CO₂ capture equipment will be installed in the dedicated common area. For all cases, conditioning and storage is assumed to be installed in the common area, separated from the process section. Figure 5.4 shows the CO₂ process scheme in the case of no mixing of the flue gases, which will be used as a reference case. A total cost of 303.5 € per tonne of CO₂ captured was calculated in this case.

Figure 5.4: CO₂ capture process scheme for the Skutskär mill in the case of no mixing of the flue gases.

Figure 5.5 instead shows the different opportunities considered for capture process configurations, which assumes that flue gases are mixed at some point in the process. The calculated equipment sizes and costs are shown in Table 5.6.

Figure 5.5: Different CO₂ capture scheme options analyzed for the Skutskär mill.

Table 5.6: Results for the CO₂ capture scheme options for the Skutskär mill. Costs are preliminary estimates for capture using MEA and should only be used to compare the different capture schemes.

		A	B		C			D		E	
			Column 1	Column 2	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 1	Column 2	Column 1	Column 2
DCC	Diameter [m]	4.1	2.9	4.1	2.9	4.1	-	2.9	4.1	2.9	4.1
	Height [m]	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	-	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0
Absorber(s)	Diameter [m]	9.6	9.6	-	3.3	4.4	7.9	5.6	7.9	5.6	7.9
	Height [m]	30.8	30.8	-	28.7	29.1	30.3	29.6	30.3	29.6	30.3
Desorber(s)	Diameter [m]	5.7	5.7	-	5.7	-	-	3.2	4.6	5.7	-
	Height [m]	16.7	16.7	-	16.7	-	-	16.7	16.7	16.6	-
Cost of CO ₂ capture (€/tCO ₂ captured)		69.6	69.9		69.8			76.4		69.6	
Cost of CO ₂ avoided (€/tCO ₂ . avoided)		92.8	93.3		93.2			102.0		92.8	

As expected, using a single capture train for each source is not cost-effective. Thus, merging of at least parts of the capture and conditioning steps allows significant cost savings. The configuration chosen in this study corresponds to configuration A, where all CO₂ sources are mixed and sent to a common CO₂ capture train. As expected, equipment sizes for configuration A are the largest, but, compared with the layout of the plant, they can be accommodated. It is worth noting, however, that the results show very similar costs for all configurations as long as they include a common desorber and conditioning plant (i.e., for configuration A, B, C and E), independently of whether individual or common absorbers were assumed. This implies that individual absorbers could have been an interesting alternative to the mixed flue gas design that was chosen.

It should be stressed that the costs reported in Table 5.6 are rough estimates using MEA as solvent and without considering process integration, and therefore should only be used to compare the different capture configuration options. More accurate cost estimations are part of further work.

5.2 Thermal requirements for the capture processes

5.2.1 Reference amine-based capture technology

For the capture scenarios considered for the Skutskär mill, the stripper reboiler of the reference capture process (using the AMP/PZ solvent) is modelled to operate at a temperature of 116.5 °C and the heat duty is estimated to 2940 kJ/kg CO₂ captured. For Langerbrugge, the corresponding values are 115.1 °C and 2980 kJ/kg CO₂. Other heating and cooling requirements for the reference capture process (and the liquefaction plant) as integrated in the two mills have been shared between the partners in WP5. These are used to establish the net heating and cooling demand characteristics for the capture and liquefaction plant, in order to enable targeting of the potential heat integration with the respective mill (see Section 5.3.1 for illustration of such results for the reference capture integration scenario in the Skutskär mill).

5.2.2 CO₂ Solutions by Saipem technology

For the capture scenarios defined to use the CO₂ Solutions by Saipem technology, the thermal requirements will be established by using the process model described in Section 4.2 to simulate the capture process with the design specifications reported in Sections 5.1.1 and 5.1.3, respectively. When the simulation results are available, these will be used for energy targeting studies similar to those reported in Section 5.3.1 for the reference capture integration scenario using the reference capture technology.

The heat supply for the reboiler is assumed to be hot water with a supply temperature of 85 °C and a return temperature of 75 °C. It should be noted that if a heat source is available at temperatures above 90 °C, this can only be used together with an intermediate heat exchanger in order to ensure a reboiler skin temperature below 85–90 °C, avoiding the risk of thermal degradation of the enzyme.

Based on simulations performed for other work packages in the ACCESS project, the specific heat duty for the reboiler can be expected to be similar to the specific heat duty for the reference amine-based capture technology. Most of the cooling demands of the capture process are at low temperatures, leaving few opportunities to recover heat from the capture plant to use in the host mill. However, some of the heat from interstage coolers in the CO₂ compression train is expected to be available at relatively high temperatures and might be relevant to consider for heat integration.

5.3 Definition of heat integration assumptions in the capture integration scenarios

5.3.1 Heat integration in the Skutskär mill

Figure 5.6 shows the potential heat integration between the mill (without lignin extraction) and the reference capture and liquefaction process. The GCC of the carbon capture and liquefaction process is shown as the foreground curve and the GCC of the pulp process is shown as the background curve. The shifted pinch temperature of the carbon capture and liquefaction process is 122 °C, and since most of the excess heat from the pulping process is available below 100 °C, the opportunity for heat integration between the two processes is very limited.

Figure 5.6: Split GCCs illustrating the potential heat integration between the reference carbon capture and liquefaction process (foreground) and the kraft pulping process of the Skutskär mill, including the high-temperature heat from the recovery boiler (background). ($\Delta T_{min} = 10 \text{ K}$)

Figure 5.6 shows that the high-temperature heat generated by combustion of black liquor in the recovery boiler of the mill has the potential to cover the combined heat demand of the carbon capture process and the mill. This will, however, require that almost all the high temperature excess heat is used for process heating. Currently this heat is used to generate high-pressure steam, which is run through a back-pressure steam turbine to co-generate electricity while also providing steam for heating the mill's processes. If the heat demand of the carbon capture process should also be covered by the recovery boiler heat, this would require that the steam turbines are bypassed. Consequently, this would come at the cost of greatly reducing the electricity production. An alternative would be to use a utility boiler to generate enough additional steam to allow for co-generation of electricity in steam turbines, while providing the necessary amount of steam to the process. This would increase the fuel use at the mill, but the marginal electrical efficiency of additional fuel use would be close to 100 %.

In the capture scenario defined to use the CO₂ Solutions by Saipem technology for the carbon capture, the heat required for regeneration can be provided by hot water with a supply temperature of 85 °C, which is significantly lower than the temperature required for the reference capture

process, and more importantly, well below the pinch temperature of the Skutskär mill. This means that it can be possible to recover excess heat from the pulping process to cover some of the heat demand for capture. To investigate the potential for excess heat recovery to supply (parts of) the heat required for the regeneration of solvent, the GCC of the pulp mill was analyzed. To enable a closer look at the curve in the temperature range below the pinch temperature, the GCC excluding the recovery boiler heat is shown in Figure 5.7. The figure also indicates the potential target for recovery of heat to produce hot water with a supply temperature of 85 °C and a return temperature of 75 °C. Note that the temperatures are shifted in the GCC, assuming a ΔT_{\min} of 10 K.

Figure 5.7: Grand Composite Curve of the Skutskär mill, showing the net heating and cooling demands of the pulping process ($\Delta T_{\min} = 10$ K), and indicating the theoretical potential for hot water production (supply temperature of 85 °C and return temperature of 75 °C) through heat recovery from process excess heat.

Figure 5.7 shows that the potential hot water production from excess heat is about 32 MW. This corresponds to approximately 30 % of the heat demand for the reference capture process, and can be expected to represent a similar share of the heat demand for the CO₂ Solutions process.

The GCC of the Skutskär mill is similar to that of many other kraft mills with regards to the significant (theoretical) availability of excess heat at temperatures below approximately 100 °C. However, compared to other mills the Skutskär mill has relatively more of this heat available at temperatures around 100 °C, while many other mills have most of this excess heat at even lower temperatures, e.g. around 60°C and below. Also in the Skutskär mill, energy efficiency measures are being investigated, which if implemented would result in less excess heat being available at this temperature level. On the other hand, such measures would improve the steam balance of the mill, making more primary steam available for capture without the need for by-passing turbines or using more fuel.

5.3.1.1 Consequences of lignin extraction on the heat integration potential

In our analysis of carbon capture at the Skutskär mill, in addition to the current mill configuration and normal operation, a second configuration was defined, in which it was assumed that lignin

extraction has been implemented in the mill (see Table 5.1). For this mill configuration, only integration with the reference capture process is considered.

As mentioned in Section 5.1.2, the major effect of lignin extraction on the mass and heat flows of the mill is connected to the operation of the recovery boilers. When lignin is extracted from the black liquor and no longer combusted in the recovery boiler, the steam production in the boiler is reduced. The lost heat production must either be met by reductions in steam use in the mill processes or steam turbines, or by increased steam production (with corresponding CO₂ emissions) in utility boilers. Moreover, the lignin-lean black liquor and wash water streams returned from the lignin extraction plant means more water must be evaporated in the evaporation section, which consequently requires a higher heat demand.

Based on the integration assessment shown in Figure 5.6, the minimum heating and cooling requirements were determined for the reference capture integration scenario. Minimum heating and cooling requirements were estimated in the same way also for the mill with both lignin extraction and carbon capture. The energy targeting results, as well as the estimated steam production in the recovery boiler, are presented in Table 5.7, which also compares the results with corresponding heat production values and energy targets for the mill without carbon capture.

Table 5.7: Heat production in the recovery boiler and estimated key energy targets for the Skutskär mill in the capture integration scenarios with the reference capture process. Corresponding values for the mill without carbon capture are shown for comparison.

	Mill without carbon capture (for comparison)	Carbon capture only	Lignin extraction and carbon capture
Recovery boiler primary steam production [MW]	286	286	248
Recovery boiler high temperature excess heat [MW]	110	1	0
Minimum hot utility requirements [MW]	0	0	26

Table 5.7 shows that if the pulping process is modified to extract lignin from the black liquor, the recovery boiler would not generate enough heat to meet the minimum heat requirements of a carbon capture process integrated with the mill. For this mill configuration, there would be a deficit of heat from the recovery boiler, even if no co-generation of electricity is assumed. This is mainly due to the reduced heat production in the recovery boiler when the extracted lignin is no longer being combusted, thus reducing the heating value of the black liquor fuel sent to the recovery boiler. To balance the deficit of heat, additional hot utility must be provided, e.g., by a power boiler.

5.3.1.2 Effects on fuel demand and power generation potential

For further investigation of utility boiler requirements and potential steam turbine power generation for the scenarios with the reference capture process in the Skutskär mill, the integration of a steam turbine cycle was also estimated using foreground / background analysis (see Section 3.1). Two cases representing different trade-offs between fuel use and electricity generation were investigated. In the first case, minimized fuel use is prioritized, and in the second case, maximized back-pressure steam turbine electricity generation is prioritized. The results are presented in Table 5.8.

In Table 5.8 it is shown that, if minimizing fuel use, it is only necessary to use a utility boiler when both lignin extraction and carbon capture are implemented in the mill. However, when back-pressure electricity production is maximized, the case with only carbon capture as well as the case with both lignin extraction and carbon capture require significant use of a utility boiler. Note that when neither carbon capture nor lignin extraction are integrated in the mill, additional utility boiler use would not be required at all (based on the theoretical energy targets) even when back-pressure electricity production is maximized since the heat available from the recovery boiler is sufficient to cover the demands of the integrated mill and steam cycle.

Table 5.8: Estimated minimum utility boiler heat production and maximum potential power generation from the back-pressure steam turbine under different assumptions about the trade-off between fuel use and electricity generation. Results for the Skutskär mill in the capture integration scenarios with the reference capture process. Corresponding values for the mill without carbon capture are shown for comparison.

		<i>Mill without carbon capture (for comparison)</i>	Carbon capture only	Lignin extraction and carbon capture
Minimized fuel use in utility boiler	Utility boiler steam production [MW]	0	0	25.7
	Back-pressure power production [MW]	50.6	1.3	0
Maximized back-pressure electricity production	Utility boiler steam production [MW]	0	61.2	85.6
	Back-pressure power production [MW]	50.6	62.5	59.9

The potential power generation varies somewhat between the process configurations when the back-pressure electricity production is maximized, depending on how large the heat requirements are for the integrated processes. The two process configurations with carbon capture (with or without lignin extraction) show a very similar increase in electricity production potential when comparing maximized power generation with minimized fuel use. Consequently, the corresponding increase in power boiler use is also very similar.

The results should also be put in relation to existing boiler and turbine capacities in the mill. In the Skutskär mill, existing boiler and turbine capacity is currently fully utilized, at least during certain periods of the year. Consequently, any increase in targeted fuel use or power generation would require investment in new boiler or turbine capacity, respectively.

Overall, the results show that the integration of the reference amine-based carbon capture plant strongly affects the energy balances of the mill, and if lignin extraction is implemented in the mill where carbon capture is integrated, the energy balances become even more constrained. In the case where lignin extraction is implemented in the mill, the theoretical energy targets show that additional fuel use in a utility boiler would be required independently of the trade-off between fuel use and power co-generation.

It may be recalled that CO₂ capture from the utility boiler was not considered, partly due to large operational variations in load. Noting, however, the significant increase in required base load steam production in the utility boiler in the capture scenarios with maximized power generation and/or lignin extraction, it may become more attractive to consider CO₂ capture also from the

utility boiler in these scenarios. More specifically, partial capture on base load emissions could be an interesting option. The capture potential and consequences on mill energy balances of that would, however, require further study.

In the scenarios where the capture technology is defined to be the CO₂ Solutions by Saipem process, the effects on overall fuel use and power generation targets are expected to be less pronounced. The results from the targeting of excess heat availability in the pulp mill indicated that a significant share of the hot water required for solvent regeneration can be covered by excess heat if this low-temperature capture process is used (see e.g. Figure 5.7 and the subsequent paragraph). This implies that the need for additional fuel can be reduced and/or more high-temperature heat will remain available for co-generation of power in the mill. Assuming that the specific reboiler duty is similar to the reference capture process, about 30 % of the heat demand can be covered by excess heat instead of by steam extracted from the mill's steam turbine cycle.

5.3.1.3 Effects on carbon flows in the Skutskär mill

Figure 5.8 shows estimated biogenic carbon flows for the Skutskär mill for scenarios where a reference capture plant is integrated at the mill. The figure also compares this with the carbon flows for an ideally heat integrated mill without carbon capture. Results are presented both for a case when fuel use is minimized (Figure 5.8A) and for a case when back-pressure steam turbine power generation is maximized (Figure 5.8B). Note that the figure only shows carbon flows of product and exhaust streams, which are affected by the integration of the carbon capture and/or the lignin extraction plant.

Figure 5.8: Comparison of carbon flows for different heat integrated configurations of the Skutskär mill. A) minimizing fuel use, and B) maximizing back-pressure steam turbine power generation.

Figure 5.8 shows that if carbon capture is integrated in a mill with lignin extraction, more biogenic carbon would be converted to products (compared to integrating carbon capture in a mill without lignin extraction). However, due to the unfavourable energy balances of this mill configuration, it would also result in more carbon being emitted (since the CO₂ from the utility boiler is not assumed to be captured). If only considering the carbon efficiency of the process, this mill configuration would perform worse than the carbon capture configuration without lignin

extraction, since the increase in emitted carbon is higher than the increase in recovered carbon in products.

Using only carbon efficiency as performance indicator would, however, not capture the usefulness of the recovered carbon and the value of the different product streams. Obviously, the potential for high-value applications is expected to be much higher for lignin than for both CO₂ and the solid biomass fuels used in the utility boiler.

The analysis of direct impacts on carbon flows in the mill would also not capture the indirect effects on CO₂ emissions resulting from the changes in mill's (net) electricity balance. Comparing cases A and B in Figure 5.8 shows how the maximization of electric power generation clearly increases the amount of emitted (biogenic) carbon (from the mill site) compared to the scenario where fuel use is minimized, due to increased emissions from the utility boiler. However, in a wider systems perspective, the effects on CO₂ emissions would be strongly dependent also on the emissions intensity of grid electricity generation, which would be replaced by the electricity from the mill.

Note that the results for carbon flows (similarly to the results for energy balances) are affected by the assumption about 90 % capture of CO₂ from the flue gases. With a lower capture rate, it would be possible to avoid increased wood fuel use and associated emissions from the bark boiler. On the other hand, less carbon would be captured and the emitted carbon from the recovery boiler would be higher.

5.3.1.4 Heat pumping opportunities for the Skutskär mill

Previous assessments of the potential for using heat pumps to provide heat to the mill processes have shown that the costs for installing and operating a heat pump are too high to make this an economically viable option. However, most of the mill's own process heat demands are at temperatures corresponding to the temperature of low-pressure steam (145 °C), which would require a significant temperature lift for the heat pump, leading to low coefficient of performance (COP), i.e., a high specific power requirement per unit of heat delivered. On the other hand, the heat requirement for regeneration of the AMP/PZ solvent in the reference capture process is at a significantly lower temperature (116 °C), thereby allowing for a smaller temperature lift and a better performance.

To investigate the potential for using a heat pump to supply (parts of) the heat required for the regeneration of solvent, the GCC of the pulp mill was analyzed. Figure 5.6 shows the GCC of the pulping process including the high-temperature heat released from the recovery boiler. To enable a detailed analysis of the excess heat available below the pinch temperature (which is relevant for heat pumping), the GCC excluding the recovery boiler heat is shown in Figure 5.9.

Figure 5.9: Grand Composite Curve of the Skutskär mill, showing the net heating and cooling demands of the pulping process ($\Delta T_{min} = 10$ K), and indicating a potential source of excess heat for a heat pump.

The GCC shows that there is a significant (net) cooling demand at a (shifted) temperature of around 100 °C. Due to the high temperature of this latent heat source, it seems very promising as a potential heat source for a heat pump. Further investigation of the data behind the GCC reveals that this heat source is (very) low pressure steam from the black liquor flashes. This further strengthens the attractiveness of using this for a heat pump, since the temperature can be achieved by directly compressing the steam in a mechanical vapour recompression (MVR) heat pump, thus avoiding the use of a working media, and one heat exchanger unit and the corresponding temperature difference for heat exchange. More specifically, the excess heat source consists of 28 MW of flash steam of a temperature of 102 °C. With the reboiler of the desorber in the capture plant at 116 °C (benchmark solvent), and a minimum temperature difference for heat exchange of 10 °C, the required temperature lift for the heat pump would be 24 °C. Assuming a Carnot efficiency factor of 50–70 %, it should be possible to achieve a COP for the heat pump between 8.3 and 11.6. With the 28 MW of excess heat as a heat source, this would make it possible to supply 31–32 MW of the heat required for the capture process through such MVR solution. The corresponding electric power demand for the MVR would be 2.6–3.8 MW.

The potential of an MVR as a heat supply option for the carbon capture process can be compared to the total heat requirement of the reference capture plant, which is 108 MW. The heat pump can consequently only cover a smaller share of the total heat requirement, and is further disadvantaged by its expected high capital costs (mainly attributable to the steam compressor). However, the heat pump potential is comparable to the minimum additional utility boiler load in the scenario with lignin extraction. This could mean that a heat pump could replace the need for investing in a new power boiler, which would otherwise imply another high capital cost.

However, even if the GCC shows that, theoretically, this heat could be made available, parts of it are currently used to cover other heat demands in the mill, and significant retrofits of the heat recovery system might be needed to release the heat. Furthermore, the mill is currently working on different ways of improving their energy efficiency, and the steam from the black liquor flashes has been in focus for several measures under investigation, among others, to replace primary steam

use in the digester. If these measures are implemented, the excess heat might no longer be available. On the other hand, such measures would reduce the primary steam demand of the mill, and thereby make it possible to use more low-pressure steam directly for the capture process without losses in electricity generation or need for additional fuel use.

To summarize, the heat pumping opportunity seems to be very promising under some conditions, i.e., especially when a heat pump could make it possible to avoid investing in a new boiler. However, there are large uncertainties regarding whether the theoretically indicated availability of the excess steam will remain after future efficiency improvements in the mill and if it then will be possible to release this steam in a cost-efficient way. Consequently, the heat pumping option has not been included further in the definition of capture integration scenarios.

5.3.2 Heat integration in the Langerbrugge mill

Most of the production process in Langerbrugge mill is a low-temperature process, and process cooling typically occurs at temperatures below 50-60 °C implying a lack of heat sources that could be utilized for enhanced process heat recovery or for supply of heat to a capture plant.

In the mill, higher temperatures are mainly needed for the heat supply for the paper machines, which requires the use of low-pressure steam. The total steam consumption for the two production lines (L3 and L4) and for district heating (DH) are presented in Table 5.9 together with the steam production in the two power plants (EC1 and EC2). Steam production in auxiliary boilers (typically less than 0.5 MW during normal operation) is neglected. Note that steam consumed for operation of the power plants, e.g., for feed water and air pre-heating (ca 14 MW) is not included in the table.

As shown in Table 5.9, the power boilers produce more than enough steam to cover the steam demand for the paper machines, which allows for significant generation of electric power. There are two steam turbines at Langerbrugge, a back-pressure turbine (TG1) using steam from EC1 and a condensing turbine with a steam extraction (TG2) using steam from EC2. The electricity production of the two turbines is shown in Table 5.10.

Table 5.9: Steam production and consumption at Langerbrugge paper mill.

Steam production [MW]	EC1	54.0
	EC2	126.1
	Total	180.2
Steam consumption [MW]	L3	19.8
	L4	34.6
	DH	12.6
	Total	67.0

Table 5.10: Average electricity production in the steam turbines.

Electricity production [MW]	TG1	10.2
	TG2	37.5
	Total	47.7

Consequently, steam can be extracted from the steam turbine cycle to supply heat to the capture process, but with a corresponding loss of steam turbine power generation. The total steam production of the mill (180 MW) should be more than sufficient for covering the heat demand of the mill (ca 67 MW + 14 MW) as well as a new capture plant (roughly 65 MW if assuming a specific reboiler duty of 3 MJ/kg). As far as possible, this steam should be extracted at low pressure from the condensing turbine, thus only leading to a smaller loss of power generation since the condensing stage has a low efficiency. If more steam is needed, there is also the possibility to bypass one of the turbines.

There may also be opportunities to heat integrate the capture plant with the mill by recovering excess heat from the capture process. In Task 5.1, two ways of utilizing excess heat from a carbon capture process were identified connected to heating requirements for return condensate in the feed water system of the mill.

The first identified heat demand that could potentially be covered by excess heat from a capture process is a stream of condensate returning from the paper machines to the feedwater tank. The stream has an average mass flow of 19 kg/s and a temperature of 58 °C. It can be heated to the temperature of the feedwater tank temperature to save steam that is used for heating in the feed water tank.

The second opportunity for utilization of excess heat is the heating of condensate from the turbine condenser of the condensing turbine before it is returned to the feedwater tank. However, if steam is extracted from the condensing turbine (before the condensing stage) in order to supply heat to the capture process, this condensate flow will be reduced (or completely eliminated), and this opportunity will therefore not be considered further.

6 CONCLUDING SUMMARY

The work on carbon capture integration in pulp and paper mills has focused on Stora Enso's kraft pulp mill located in Skutskär (Sweden) and Stora Enso's recycled paper mill located in Langerbrugge (Belgium). The capture integration scenarios to be investigated in WP5 have been defined according to the specifications and assumptions presented in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1. Definition of capture integration scenarios.

Capture integration scenario	Mill	Emission sources	Capture design specs.	Capture technology	Heat integration	Fuel/ electricity trade-off
Skutskär – Reference	Skutskär	Lime kilns (LK) and recovery boilers (SP6 & SP7)	See Section 5.1.1	Reference amine	Optimized	Min fuel
						Max power
Skutskär – Saipem				CO2 Solutions	Optimized	Min fuel
						Max power
Skutskär – Strategic	Skutskär with lignin extraction	Lime kilns (LK) and recovery boilers (SP6 & SP7)	Scaled from reference scenario	Reference amine	Optimized	Min fuel
						Max power
Langerbrugge – Reference	Langerbrugge	Power boilers, EC1 & EC2	See Section 5.1.3	Reference amine	Current	Constant fuel
Langerbrugge – Saipem				CO2 Solutions	Current	Constant fuel

Relevant flue gas data (temperatures, flowrates and compositions) and capture plant requirements were established for both mills as well as indicative annual operating hours. Process models have been established for both the reference amine-based capture technology (with AMP/PZ as a solvent), the CO2 Solutions by Saipem technology and for the liquefaction plant. In particular, the models include operating characteristics regarding heat and temperature requirements for solvent regeneration. In subsequent tasks these process models will be used for simulation of the defined capture integration scenarios in order to estimate capital costs.

Due to limited opportunities for heat recovery in the Langerbrugge mill, the capture integration scenarios for the Langerbrugge mill were defined based on actual, current thermal flows, and heat supply for the capture plant is assumed to be achieved by extracting steam from the existing steam turbine cycles. Assessment of the mill's energy balances indicate that the total steam production of the mill (180 MW) should be more than sufficient for covering the heat demand of the mill as well as a new capture plant (roughly 150 MW in total), but would be associated with loss of power generation. If the simulations of the capture processes indicate that there are possibilities to recover heat from the capture processes at sufficiently high temperature, there may also be opportunities to use heat from the capture plant to cover heating requirements for return condensate in the feed water system of the mill.

In the scenarios considered for the Skutskär mill the energy balances have been defined assuming optimized heat integration within the mill as well as between the mill and the capture and liquefaction process. The optimized heat cascade for the mill was established using a methodology based on Pinch Analysis. For the optimization, scenarios have also been defined representing different trade-offs between fuel use and co-generation of power.

The results obtained for the Skutskär mill show that the integration of the reference amine-based carbon capture plant strongly affects the energy balances of the mill. If fuel use is minimized, the amount of excess heat available for back-pressure electricity production is reduced to close to zero. If lignin extraction is assumed to be implemented in the mill, the energy balances become even more constrained when integrating the capture process, since the capture process increases the minimum steam requirement significantly, at the same time as extraction of lignin reduces the steam production in the recovery boiler. In this scenario, the theoretical energy targets show that additional fuel use in a utility boiler would be required independently of the trade-off between fuel use and power co-generation. This would result in more (biogenic) carbon dioxide being emitted since the emissions from the utility boiler are not assumed to be captured. On the other hand, more carbon leaves the mill as a valuable by-product, in the form of the extracted lignin. When production of back-pressure electricity is prioritized instead of minimizing fuel use, additional heat supplied by the utility boiler provides an opportunity for generating back-pressure electricity with very high efficiency. The optimum design and operation of the steam utility system depends on the prices of fuel and electricity, but also on available capacities in existing turbines and utility boilers. In this context, it is worth noting that if the mill has implemented lignin extraction, the boiler capacity is more likely to become a limiting factor, possibly requiring new investments.

As part of the reference scenario for the Skutskär mill, heat pumping opportunities have also been investigated. The analysis showed a significant theoretical potential for heat pumping (up to 32 MW of heat delivered with a power input of 3-4 MW) to cover parts of the heat requirement for the capture process in the Skutskär mill. However, due to large uncertainties regarding the actual future availability and cost of releasing the excess heat needed for the heat pump, the heat pumping option has not been included further in the definition of capture integration scenarios.

In the capture scenarios defined to use the CO₂ Solutions by Saipem technology for the carbon capture, the heat required for regeneration can be provided by hot water with a supply temperature of 85 °C, which is a significantly lower temperature than that required for the reference capture process (116 °C plus temperature difference for heat exchange). The results from the targeting of excess heat availability at the Skutskär mill indicated that 32 MW of hot water could be generated through recovery of excess heat. Assuming that the specific reboiler duty is similar to the reference capture process, about 30 % of the heat demand can be supplied by excess heat instead of by steam extracted from the mill's steam turbine cycle. This implies that the need for additional fuel can be reduced and/or more high-temperature heat will remain available for co-generation of power in the mill.

7 REFERENCES

- Akbari, M., Oyedun, A.O., Jain, S., Kumar, A., 2018. Options for the conversion of pulp and paper mill by-products in Western Canada. *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assess.* 26, 83–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SETA.2017.10.003>
- Anantharaman, R., Roussanaly, S., Westman, S.F., Husebye, J., 2013. Selection of Optimal CO₂ Capture Plant Capacity for Better Investment Decisions. *Energy Procedia*, GHGT-11 Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies, 18-22 November 2012, Kyoto, Japan 37, 7039–7045. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2013.06.640>
- Biermann, M., Harvey, S., Kjærstad, J., Anantharaman, R., Fu, C., Reyes-Lúa, A., Roussanaly, S., Jordal, K., Lundqvist, K., Gorset, O., Hoballah, R., Wanderley, R., Seglem, H., 2022. Preem CCS - Synthesis of main project findings and insights.
- Deng, H., Roussanaly, S., Skaugen, G., 2019. Techno-economic analyses of CO₂ liquefaction: Impact of product pressure and impurities. *Int. J. Refrig.* 103, 301–315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrefrig.2019.04.011>
- Equinor, 2019. Northern Lights Project Concept report (No. RE-PM673-00001).
- Fajardy, M., Morris, J., Gurgel, A., Herzog, H., Mac Dowell, N., Paltsev, S., 2021. The economics of bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) deployment in a 1.5 °C or 2 °C world. *Glob. Environ. Change* 68, 102262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102262>
- Feron, P.H.M., Cousins, A., Jiang, K., Zhai, R., Garcia, M., 2020. An update of the benchmark post-combustion CO₂-capture technology. *Fuel* 273, 117776. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2020.117776>
- Google, 2023. Google Maps [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.google.com/maps/>
- Haaker, A., 2015. LignoBoost-anläggning från Valmet överlämnad till Stora Enso [WWW Document]. *Bioenergitidningen*. URL <https://bioenergitidningen.se/lignoboost-anlaggning-fran-valmet-overlamnad-till-stora-enso/>
- Hansen, S.V., Steinmann, Z.J.N., Daioglou, V., Čengić, M., Van Vuuren, D.P., Huijbregts, M.A.J., 2022. Global implications of crop-based bioenergy with carbon capture and storage for terrestrial vertebrate biodiversity. *GCB Bioenergy* 14, 307–321. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12911>
- Harvey, S., Morandin, M., Berntsson, T., Papadokostantakis, S., Svensson, E., 2023. Analysis and synthesis of utility systems, including heat pumping and combined heat and power, in: Klemeš, J.J. (Ed.), *Handbook of Process Integration (PI)*. Woodhead Publishing, pp. 187–215.
- Hitta.se, 2023. Interactive map [WWW Document]. [hitta.se](https://www.hitta.se/kartan). URL <https://www.hitta.se/kartan>.
- Hubbe, M.A., Alén, R., Paleologou, M., Kannangara, M., Kihlman, J., 2019. Lignin recovery from spent alkaline pulping liquors using acidification, membrane separation, and related processing steps: A review. *BioResources* 14, 2300–2351.
- Jakobsen, J.P., Roussanaly, S., Brunsvold, A., Anantharaman, R., 2014. A Tool for Integrated Multi-criteria Assessment of the CCS Value Chain. *Energy Procedia*, 12th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies, GHGT-12 63, 7290–7297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.11.765>

- Kemp, I.C., Shiun Lim, J., 2020. Process change and evolution, in: Pinch Analysis for Energy and Carbon Footprint Reduction - User Guide to Process Integration for the Efficient Use of Energy. Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Klemeš, J.J., 2023. Handbook of process integration (PI): minimisation of energy and water use, waste and emissions.
- Kuparinen, K., Vakkilainen, E., Tynjälä, T., 2019. Biomass-based carbon capture and utilization in kraft pulpmills. *Mitig. Adapt. Strateg. Glob. Change* 24, 1213–1230.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-018-9833-9>
- Li, H., Frailie, P.T., Rochelle, G.T., Chen, J., 2014. Thermodynamic modeling of piperazine/2-aminomethylpropanol/CO₂/water. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 117, 331–341.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2014.06.026>
- Morandin, M., 2017. MAT4PI: A Matlab based framework for process integration studies - User guide.
- Nwaoha, C., Tontiwachwuthikul, P., 2019. Carbon dioxide capture from pulp mill using 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol and monoethanolamine blend: Techno-economic assessment of advanced process configuration. *Appl. Energy* 250, 1202–1216.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.05.097>
- Onarheim, K., Santos, S., Kangas, P., Hankalin, V., 2017a. Performance and costs of CCS in the pulp and paper industry part 1: Performance of amine-based post-combustion CO₂ capture. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 59, 58–73.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2017.02.008>
- Onarheim, K., Santos, S., Kangas, P., Hankalin, V., 2017b. Performance and cost of CCS in the pulp and paper industry part 2: Economic feasibility of amine-based post-combustion CO₂ capture. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 66, 60–75.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJGGC.2017.09.010>
- Optimized Gas Treating Inc., 2021. ProTreat 6.6. <https://www.ogtrt.com/page/protreat>
- Pola, L., Collado, S., Oulego, P., Díaz, M., 2022. Kraft black liquor as a renewable source of value-added chemicals. *Chem. Eng. J.* 448, 137728.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEJ.2022.137728>
- Rosa, L., Sanchez, D.L., Mazzotti, M., 2021. Assessment of carbon dioxide removal potential via BECCS in a carbon-neutral Europe. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 14, 3086–3097.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/D1EE00642H>
- Roussanaly, S., Anantharaman, R., 2017. Cost-optimal CO₂ capture ratio for membrane-based capture from different CO₂ sources. *Chem. Eng. J.* 327, 618–628.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2017.06.082>
- Roussanaly, S., Brunsvold, A.L., Hognes, E.S., 2014. Benchmarking of CO₂ transport technologies: Part II – Offshore pipeline and shipping to an offshore site. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 28, 283–299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2014.06.019>
- Roussanaly, S., Jakobsen, J.P., Hognes, E.H., Brunsvold, A.L., 2013. Benchmarking of CO₂ transport technologies: Part I—Onshore pipeline and shipping between two onshore areas. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 19, 584–594.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2013.05.031>
- Smith, P., Davis, S.J., Creutzig, F., Fuss, S., Minx, J., Gabrielle, B., Kato, E., Jackson, R.B., Cowie, A., Krieglner, E., van Vuuren, D.P., Rogelj, J., Ciais, P., Milne, J., Canadell, J.G.,

- McCollum, D., Peters, G., Andrew, R., Krey, V., Shrestha, G., Friedlingstein, P., Gasser, T., Grüber, A., Heidug, W.K., Jonas, M., Jones, C.D., Kraxner, F., Littleton, E., Lowe, J., Moreira, J.R., Nakicenovic, N., Obersteiner, M., Patwardhan, A., Rogner, M., Rubin, E., Sharifi, A., Torvanger, A., Yamagata, Y., Edmonds, J., Yongsung, C., 2016. Biophysical and economic limits to negative CO₂ emissions. *Nat. Clim. Change* 6, 42–50. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2870>
- Svensson, E., Morandin, M., Harvey, S., 2019. Characterization and visualization of industrial excess heat for different levels of on-site process heat recovery. *Int. J. Energy Res.* 43, 7988–8003. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.4787>
- Téguia, C.D., Albers, R., Stuart, P.R., 2017. Analysis of economically viable lignin-based biorefinery strategies implemented within a kraft pulp mill. *Tappi J.* 16, 157–169. <https://doi.org/10.32964/tj16.3.157>
- Tomani, P., 2010. The LignoBoost process. *Cellul. Chem. Technol.* 44, 53–58.
- Välimäki, E., Niemi, P., Haaga, K., 2010. A Case Study on the Effects of Lignin Recovery on Recovery Boiler Operation, in: *International Chemical Recovery Conference*. Williamsburg, VA, USA. <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.1777.5046>
- Voldsund, M., Gardarsdottir, S.O., De Lena, E., Pérez-Calvo, J.-F., Jamali, A., Berstad, D., Fu, C., Romano, M., Roussanaly, S., Anantharaman, R., Hoppe, H., Sutter, D., Mazzotti, M., Gazzani, M., Cinti, G., Jordal, K., 2019. Comparison of Technologies for CO₂ Capture from Cement Production—Part 1: Technical Evaluation. *Energies* 12, 559. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12030559>
- Zhang, W., Chen, J., Luo, X., Wang, M., 2017. Modelling and process analysis of post-combustion carbon capture with the blend of 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol and piperazine. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 63, 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2017.04.018>